

D2.4 Data products validation report

**Wp2: Earth Observation data products and
services**

**Oscar Rosario Belfiore, Salvatore Falanga Bolognesi, Guido
D'Urso, Carlo De Michele (ARIESPACE WP Leader)**

Input from: Alfonso Calera Belmonte, Maria Calera (AgriSat),
Violeta Domnica Poenaru (ROSA), Stelios Kotsopoulos
(AgroApps), Elena Navarro, Luciano Mateos (Feragua)

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Lead Author	Carlo De Michele	Email	carlo.demichele@ariespace.com
	ARIESPACE	Phone	0039 081 195 64 282
Other authors	Oscar Rosario Belfiore, Salvatore Falanga Bolognesi, Guido D’Urso, (ARIESPACE), Alfonso Calera Belmonte (AgriSat), Violeta Domnica Poenaru (ROSA), Alfonso Calera Belmonte, Maria Calera (AgriSat), Violeta Domnica Poenaru (ROSA), Stelios Kotsopoulos (AgroApps), Elena Navarro, Luciano Mateos (Feragua)		
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Executive summary

The overall aim of WP2 is to implement an EO methodology and production line for the services provided by DIANA project, which are:

- maps of irrigated areas;
- maps of irrigation water, consumption and/or water abstraction and
- maps of drought indices.

It includes data products and services based on a combination of EO data as well as meteorological and complementary data derived from different data sources, especially from pilot areas.

It aims to demonstrate that Earth Observation (EO) products provide key information about water abstraction through the identification of irrigation activities and the estimation of abstracted/consumed water volumes. However, like for in-situ non-EO-based approaches, this information needs to be compared to legal reference data to be able actually to detect possible cases of illegal irrigation.

This document describes the validation process of the data products provided by DIANA in 2019. During the irrigation season 2019, for each Diana pilot, the following products have been released and validated: i) Crop classification, ii) Maps of irrigated area, iii) Crop evapotranspiration, iv) Net Irrigation requirements, v) Gross irrigation requirements, vi) Meteorological products. The validation procedure follows what has been already done during the season 2018 with some improvements to achieve better accuracy of final product.

Finally, an additional methodology which **exploits information from short wave infrared (SWIR)** bands of Sentinel-2 to retrieve soil moisture, has been designed.

This activity responds to **a specific request raised from pilots** where a change in the cultivation vocation, from herbaceous crops to new tree crop plants has been detected. The detection of irrigated and non-irrigated new tree crop plant (mainly almond, walnuts, hazelnuts) and their crop water requirement in deficit condition represent two open issues. To tackle these new issues, an improvement of existing modelling has been necessary.

To this end, a cross-comparison of different methods for a) mapping irrigated orchards (distinguishing between irrigated and rainfed), and b) determining the corresponding water requirements have been performed. Two promising methods have been tested: 1) **OPTRAM model** which aims to the derivation

of a soil/vegetation moisture indicator from SWIR bands of Sentinel-2, by ARIESPACE; 2) SAR: estimation of soil moisture from SAR backscattering (TU-WIEN algorithm), by ROSA.

The **methodology based on the OPTRAM** model to detect irrigated crop has been developed in Italian pilot and further tested and transferred to the other pilot sites of DIANA in Spain and Romania. Despite the fact that this particular activity was not initially foreseen, DIANA partners believe that it could become a real advancement for the state-of-the-art.

The main results achieved demonstrate that **the OPTRAM model has the capability to distinguish the irrigated crops from not irrigated crops where other approaches fail**. The methodology can be transferred to different geographical regions, with different crop types, climate and management.

It confirms that additional information derived in the **SWIR spectrum is a valuable data source for improving irrigated areas mapping in a variety of environmental conditions**.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope of the document

As for the Deliverable 2.3, the relevant question is: How good is a dataset?

As reported in literature, validating the uncertainties in satellite data products is a very challenging task (Loew et al. ,2017)¹. In this context, can be found in literature a wide range of technical approaches - as well as methods and terminology- used by the Earth Observation (EO) communities.

The primary goal of DIANA is to provide users with tools that help them fulfil their mission and perform their daily routine operations more easily and better, and then quantifying the quality of the data products and services, is a fundamental objective to achieve.

This document details the results on the validation of the algorithms and methodologies considered to deliver the products, tools and services provided by the DIANA project.

These validation results are based on a combination of Earth Observation (EO), meteorological, modelled and *in-situ* data, collected for the different pilot areas considered in the project (Italy, Spain and Romania).

The algorithms and methodologies are described in detail in the “EO Methodology for DIANA services” (D2.1).

In the context of the data products validation, this report follows the previous "*Data products validation report (1)*" (D2.3) submitted at month 24.

In this document are also reported the results of the “*Diana Benchmark Exercise*”. A specific task delineated during technical meetings, which aims to improve the detection of irrigated areas process, taking into account the soil moisture data estimated from EO data. More details about the approaches and the algorithms tested are reported in *Section 5*.

¹ Loew, A., Bell, W., Brocca, L., Bulgin, C. E., Burdanowitz, J., Calbet, X. & Kinzel, J. (2017). Validation practices for satellite-based Earth observation data across communities. *Reviews of Geophysics*, 55(3), 779-817.

2 Italian Pilot area: Data products validation for the year 2019

For the Italian Pilot area, the data products validation was conducted following the similar procedures and methodologies adopted for the irrigation season 2018, but considering adjustments and improvements for some DIANA products. More details are summarized in Table 1 and reported in the following subsections.

DIANA PRODUCTS	Italian Pilot Area		
	2018	2019	2019 Improvements
Maps of Irrigated Areas	Thematic Accuracy [see D2.3 - paragraph 2.1]		✓
Crop Evapotranspiration	ET _p PM-FAO56 crosscheck [see D2.3 - paragraph 2.2, annex 8.1]		-
Net Irrigation Water Requirement	Crosscheck of Total Precipitation acquired from different datasets [see D2.3 - paragraph 2.3]		✓
Gross Irrigation Water Requirement	Comparison between water volume applied and GIWR from EO [see D2.3 - paragraph 2.4]		✓

Table 1 – Summary of the data validation process performed for the Italian Pilot area.

2.1 Map of irrigated areas

As was done for the irrigation season 2018, to detect the irrigated areas, a supervised classification was applied using as input data the NDVI time series. In detail, the performance achievable from 6 different Machine Learning Algorithms (MLA) were tested (Kuhn & Johnson, 2013)²:

- Artificial Neural Network (ANN),
- Boosted Decision Tree (BDTs),
- Single Decision Tree (sDTs),
- *k*-nearest neighbour (k-NN),
- Random Forest (RF),
- Support Vector Machine (SVM).

Several ground truth data were considered to train the algorithms. To this end, during the irrigation season 2019, the Sannio Alifano Consorzio staff conducted field inspections, collecting about 1500 points distributed in the whole area and balanced for the following three classes: i) Bare soil or rainfed, ii) herbaceous and iii) tree crop. Subsequently, to obtain a robust validation of the irrigated areas map, the

² Kuhn, M., & Johnson, K. (2013). Applied predictive modeling. (Vol. 26). New York: Springer.

ground truth dataset (pixels) were separated into training and test samples using random sampling stratified by class, with 25% of pixels used to train the model, and 75% of the pixel used to validate the model.

After the reference data splitting, all the variables were centred and rescaled for a better consistency, prior to the classification. The parameter tuning was performed using a 10-fold cross validation method through the R CARET package³ for each of the 6 classifiers. The tune length parameter was set to 10 in order to assess 10 values per each parameter. This last process allowed the building of the model basing on the best performing parameters.

With the aim to perform a robust benchmark, for each classification algorithms, four different data preprocessing scenarios were considered.

- **Scenario 1** - implies a classification set with the original training data and the initial number of input features (170);
- **Scenario 2** - implies a classification which was performed using a balanced training dataset built on a random oversampling method (applied to the minority class), in order to produce the same number of training samples per each class;
- **Scenario 3** - leads to a classification based on original training data with a recursive feature elimination process (based on RF), in order to reduce the number of features used as input (from 170 to 52);
- **Scenario 4** - is based on both balanced training dataset and the recursive feature elimination process (based on RF).

For each of the 24 classifications (6 Algorithms and 4 Scenarios), the performance of the thematic classification process was performed considering the classical accuracy calculation reported in the literature. The result was an error matrix in which the following measures were calculated: Producer's

³ Kuhn, Max. "The caret package." R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL [https://cran.r-project.org/package= caret](https://cran.r-project.org/package=caret) (2012).

Accuracy (PA), User's Accuracy (UA) and Overall Accuracy (OA) (Story & Congalton, 1986)⁴, (Congalton & Green, 2009)⁵ and Kappa Statistics⁶.

The outcomes of the accuracy assessment show high values of the accuracy measures for the RF in scenario 4.

The RF model in scenario 4, as explained before, is the product of a recursive features selection considering a balanced training dataset. It starts from 170 variables, and it searches for the number of features and the exact features selection what maximises the accuracy and the kappa values. In detail, by using this configuration were selected 52 features that allow reaching an overall accuracy value of 0.978 and a kappa value of 0.939.

Figure 1 – Performance achieved for the RF model (Scenario 4) in terms of Kappa value. The graph shows the results of the number of features selected (52) needed to reach the highest Kappa value.

In conclusion, the RF algorithm was selected to deliver the map of irrigated areas (Figure 2) as data products on DIANA platform.

⁴ Story, M., Congalton, R. G. (1986). Accuracy assessment: a user's perspective. *Photogrammetric Engineering & Remote Sensing*, 52(3), 397–399. <http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1530-9290.2010.00257.x>

⁵ Congalton, R. G., Green, K. (2009). *Assessing the Accuracy of Remotely Sensed Data: Principles and Practices*. The Photogrammetric Record (Vol. 2). http://doi.org/10.1111/j.1477-9730.2010.00574_2.x

⁶ A K Skidmore. Accuracy assessment of spatial information. In A Stein, F van der Meer, and B G F Gorte, editors, *Spatial statistics for remote sensing*, pages 197–209. Kluwer Academic, Dordrecht, 1999.

Figure 2 – Map of irrigated areas obtained by the RF algorithm.

The proposed methodology is based on the assumption that in areas with the hydrologic deficit typical of the semi-arid environments, as for the Mediterranean basin, the only vigorous crops are those that are irrigated.

However, if distinguishing an irrigated **herbaceous crop from a rainfed crop** is very simple, there are more difficulties to in discriminating **irrigated or not irrigated tree crops**.

For these purposes, for the irrigation season 2019, in order to improve the detection of the effective irrigated areas, in the Italian Pilot area was introduced a new approach to distinguish the irrigated tree crop from the not-irrigated tree crop, by using a novel approach based on the OPTRAM model⁷. More details are reported in the DIANA Benchmark section (see paragraph 5.1).

⁷ Sadeghi, Morteza, et al. "The optical trapezoid model: A novel approach to remote sensing of soil moisture applied to Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 observations." *Remote sensing of environment* 198 (2017): 52-68.

Figure 3 – Example of temporal NDVI and precipitation profiles of irrigated (continuo line) and non-irrigated (dot line) fields in two different locations in the US⁸

2.2 Water abstractions: ET_p , NIWR and GIWR.

The estimation of **Crop Evapotranspiration (ET_p)** was performed by the direct calculation based on the Penman-Monteith equation following the “Analytical Approach” (or “one-step”) proposed by (D’Urso and Menenti, 1995)⁹, as it was done in 2018. More details are reported in the deliverable 2.1 (Paragraph 3.2).

Considering the excellent results achieved for the irrigation season 2018 and according to several papers present in literature (D’Urso, 2010), (Akdin et al., 2014), (Vuolo et., al 2015), that confirming the accuracy of the above-mentioned method, for the irrigation season 2019, the ET_p validation process was carried out following the same procedures tested in the previous year. More details are reported in Deliverable 2.3 (Paragraph 2.2 and annex 8.1).

To validate the **Net Irrigation Water Requirements (NIWR)** data a crosscheck assessment was performed by comparing the Total Precipitation (T_p) estimated by the ERA-Interim reanalysis model (ECMWF)¹⁰ and the data recorded by the ground station of the CFM network (Centro Funzionale Multirischi) managed by the Civil Protection Department¹¹. Moreover, the PERSIANN - Cloud Classification System (PERSIANN

⁸ Ozdogan, Mutlu, and Garik Gutman. "A new methodology to map irrigated areas using multi-temporal MODIS and ancillary data: An application example in the continental US." *Remote Sensing of Environment* 112.9 (2008): 3520-3537.

⁹ D’Urso, G., Menenti, M. (1995). Mapping crop coefficients in irrigated areas from Landsat TM images. In *Remote Sensing for Agriculture, Forestry, and Natural Resources* (Vol. 2585, pp. 41-48). International Society for Optics and Photonics.

¹⁰ <https://www.ecmwf.int/en/forecasts/datasets/reanalysis-datasets/era-interim>

¹¹ <http://centrofunzionale.regione.campania.it/#/pages/dashboard>

CCS)¹² dataset was considered as well. The latter is a real-time global high-resolution (0.04° x 0.04°) satellite precipitation product developed by the Center for Hydrometeorology and Remote Sensing (CHRS) at the University of California, Irvine (UCI). In detail, thirteen CFM ground station were selected, considering their intersection with the ERA-Interim (cell size ≈ 12 Km) and PERSIANN CCS grid (cell size ≈ 4 Km) (Figure 4). Subsequently, the analysis were conducted cumulating the daily T_p values recorded in the entire irrigation season 2019. An overview of this comparison is plotted in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – CFM agrometeorological stations and their intersection with the ERA-Interim and PERSIANN-CCS grids.

¹² <https://chrsdata.eng.uci.edu/>

Figure 5 – Comparison of ERA-Interim PERSIAN-CSS and CFM total precipitation cumulated for the Irrigation season 2019.

According to the data plotted in Figure 5, the ERA-Interim data was chosen to obtain a more accurate and spatialized Net Precipitation (P_n) involved in NIWR computation process. In detail, to obtain the effective precipitation, the ERA-Interim T_p values have been reduced take into account the canopy development described by using the LAI and fractional vegetation cover (f_c) computed from the Sentinel-2 data (Braden, 1985)¹³.

¹³ Braden, H. (1985). Ein energiehaushalts-und verdunstungsmodell for wasser und stoffhaushaltsuntersuchungen landwirtschaftlich genutzer einzugsgebiete. Mittlungen Deutsche Bodenkundliche Gesellschaft. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.it/scholar?q=48.+Braden%2C+H.+Ein+Energiehaushalts-+und+Verdunstungsmodell+for+Wasser+und+Stoffhaushaltsuntersuchungen+landwirtschaftlich+genutzer+Einzugsgebiete.+Mittlungen+Dtsc+h.+Bodenkundliche+Gesellschaft+1985%2C+42%2C+294-299.&btnG=&hl=it&as_sdt=0%2C5#0

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Figure 6 – The concept of the NIWR validation process.

The validation of **Gross Irrigation Water Requirements (GIWR)** data product estimated from EO, was achieved through comparison with the actual water volume applied similarly to irrigation season 2018. Moreover, further validation was performed considering a sample of six farms. In details, the GIWR was derived from the NIWR taking into account the efficiency of the irrigation system for each farm, and comparing the subsequently the GIWR was compared with the actual water volume provided.

For the irrigation season 2019, with aim to perform a robust validation, both herbaceous crop and tree crop parcels were investigated. The results are shown in the following graph (Figure 7)

Table 2 - Specifications of farms selected.

Farm	Crop	Irrigation Period (2019)	Irrigation System
1	Hazelnut	June to August	Drip irrigation
2	Hazelnut	June to August	Drip irrigation
3	Hazelnut	August	Drip irrigation
4	Maize	June to August	Irrigation sprinkler
5	Maize	July to August	Irrigation sprinkler
6	Maize	July to August	Irrigation sprinkler

Figure 7 – Crosscheck comparison performed to validate the GIWR data products.

3 Spanish Pilot area: Data products validation for the year 2019

As mentioned, the validation approach of the data products elaborated in DIANA requires two types of processes. On one hand, those concerning the technical quality of the products, and on the other hand, the usability of these products, which is closely related to the DIANA platform that has been built. Both validation aspects required users' involvement.

Aware of the difficulty of the validation procedure, for the Spanish pilot areas, whose location is shown in Figure 8, the validation process began with the own selection of the pilot areas. Besides those already previously included, like "Mancha Oriental" and "Bembezar Margen Derecha", other demonstration areas like "Bajo Jalón" and "Tierra del Vino" were selected by the Spanish Ministry, together with the Spanish DIANA team. By this way, it is easier to involve these users to whom DIANA products are destined into the validation process from the earlier steps.

Figure 8 – Location of Spanish pilot areas, whose limits are superimposed on the Iberian Peninsula map.

3.1 Identified water managers' needs for the detection and monitoring of water abstractions

During the first year of the project, stakeholders expressed their requirements for a better knowledge of water abstractions and specifically on irrigation uses of irrigated areas and abstraction volumes. In the involved Spanish pilot area stakeholders are:

- Water users association:

- Junta Central Mancha Oriental, JCRMO (Central Board of Mancha Oriental) and
- Federación de Regantes de Andalucía, FERAGUA

- Water authorities:

- Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica, Dirección General del Agua
- River Basin Authority (Hydrological Planning Office): Júcar river, Ebro river, Duero river, Guadalquivir river

The operational requirements emerged included different aspects:

- continuous monitoring of irrigated areas and volumes abstracted from well-established areas;
- ensuring the reliability of self-declarations on water abstractions;
- optimizing field inspections to ensure compliance with legal requirements on water abstraction;
- ensuring compliance regarding seasonal water restrictions in the event of drought management.

Complementary requirements included:

- regularising historical water rights using better identification of water users;
- ex-post assessment on the implementation and efficiency of water management systems, providing different time scales (crisis or structural) as a base for to adopting future actions;
- adjustment of water prices and implementation of a volume-based fee system;
- support for irrigation scheduling to increase efficiency.

DIANA service “Non-authorized water abstraction detection and monitoring for control optimisation” designed and implemented to fulfil these requirements through three main products:

- Maps of irrigated areas
- Maps of Net Irrigation Water Requirements (Gross Irrigation Water Requirements)
- Time series of EO images

Maps of irrigated areas

The detection of irrigated areas (providing clear identification of the exact location and areal extent) requires land-use/land-cover maps that allow distinguishing irrigated from non-irrigated crops. The successful and widely used methodology implies the use of a supervised “multi-temporal classification” based on a time series of EO images. These images provide the temporal evolution of crops and vegetation during growing season through spectral reflectances, derived Vegetation Indices (like NDVI, the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index, EVI, SAVI and others), and even, when available, surface temperatures, and radar-based soil moisture by using Sentinel1 imagery. The classification process based on temporal pattern recognition is based on the resulting differences of the canopy on the parameters mentioned above that allow relating each pixel or a group of pixels to a vegetation class. The classes need to be defined from fieldwork and previous knowledge of crop phenology in a given area. The crop classification is the prerequisite for the identification of irrigated areas and the exact period of irrigation. The identification of fields where the crops growing there receive supplemental irrigation (i.e. less amount of water than required for an optimal development, but in a well-selected timeframe during the crop growing cycle, which is also named as regulated deficit irrigation) usually implies more difficulties: under this practice crops show lower contrast compared to the same non-irrigated crop. Supplemental irrigation is usually used when water stress occurs, and it is employed both in herbaceous annual crops and permanent crops. In this case, precipitations data is needed to distinguish irrigation (the vegetation index, reflecting the plant water status, does not differentiate between water coming from rainfall or irrigation).

Table 3 summaries the accuracy of the remote sensing-based classification accuracy according to both the type the crop addressed and the climate condition where the crop grows.

A benchmarking exercise has been done in DIANA, see Section 5 on this document, to tackle those Mediterranean crops like vineyard, olive, and almond, among others, which exhibit sparse ground cover and where the regulated deficit irrigation is a usual practice. This exercise tries to exploit in an integral approach new reflectance bands of Sentinel-2, like those placed on the SWIR wavelength, radar-based soil moisture from Sentinel1 imagery, and temperature from Landsat 8, besides conventional Vegetation Index time series.

Table 3 - Precision in the identification of irrigated surfaces by time series of images.

Irrigated Crops	Accuracy depending on the weather		Additional information to increase accuracy
	Semi-arid / arid	Sub humid / humid	
Annual Crops (herbaceous)			
Crops reaching full cover (80% or higher of cover fraction) such as wheat, corn, barley, tomato, potato, oilseeds, beets, fodder, etc.	Very good	Good	Multi-annual analysis Thermal Channel Image Radar Ancillary Cartography
Crops do not reach full cover, such as garlic, onions, etc.	Good	Low	
Permanent Crops (woody)			
Trees reaching full cover: Citrus, Avocado, Table Grape, tropical crops.	Good	Low	Multiannual Analysis Thermal Channel Radar Image Orthophotos Ancillary Cartography
Crops exhibiting low fractional vegetation cover: Vineyard, Olive, Almond.	Low	Very Low	

Maps of Net Irrigation Water Requirements, NIWR maps

A soil water balance following the FAO56 approach, integrating with a reflectance-based crop coefficient, herein called “EO-based soil water balance”, has been applied to the pilot areas for the 2016 to 2019 years. By this way, calculation of Net Irrigation Water Requirement, NIWR, in a pixel by pixel way and a daily step is performed by using the HidroMORE software.

The basis of irrigation water requirements calculations is:

- time-series of reflectances and vegetation index (VI) maps can be converted into maps of basal **crop coefficient**, the basic input for the widely used FAO56 model.

The Sentinel-2 constellation (providing suitable spectral imagery at 10 m of spatial resolution and a revisit time of less than a week) is a definitive tool in this approach. Interpolation of consecutive images allows to fill the gaps (e.g. due to cloud cover), and the product of basal crop coefficient and daily reference evapotranspiration from the agro-meteorological station subsequently provides daily crop water requirements on a pixel by pixel basis.

- EO-driven soil water balance, according to FAO56, enables to calculate **Net Irrigation Water Requirements** on a pixel by pixel basis. Precipitation and soil hydraulic characteristics are required.

Either the Irrigated Area maps, either the NIWR maps need to be adapted to the users' requirements. So, the raw product, usually expressed into a pixel by pixel basis is aggregated into the spatial field scale, which is the object of the water administrative rights. For NIWR products, two-time scales are utilised for temporal aggregation: monthly and annual. By this way, it is feasible to compare with authorised irrigated areas and authorised amounts of water for irrigation.

Gross Irrigation Water Requirements, GIWR, estimates from NIWR, in the way $GIWR * \epsilon = NIWR$, where the ϵ coefficient is the "bulk efficiency", which integrates all efficiencies in the water path from the source point to the root-soil layer where is available for the plants. The coefficient ϵ represents the fraction of the amount of water abstraction at the source point, reservoir, well..., which is finally putted in the soil root layer. The bulk efficiency value depends on both technical infrastructure and management; then, it is very variable. In our case, we adopt the accepted values according the usual practice.

Time series of EO images

In the framework of authorised amounts of water for irrigation, the "Annual Exploitation Plan, AEP" is a key tool. The AEP updates for each irrigation campaign and each field the authorised amount of water, by using parameters like piezometric evolution for groundwater abstractions, amount of water on the reservoirs, and so on. According to the stakeholder requirements, the AEP compliance enforcement requires continuous monitoring during the whole irrigation campaign.

Time series of images provides valuable help for monitoring AEP continuously when the images are provided in real-time way. It requires some infrastructure for delivering the images in a proper way for helping the field inspection, what is accomplished by the DIANA platform. Table 4 shows the products delivered to the users for the Spanish pilot areas submitted for validation by the users, according to their requirements.

Additionally, the time series of images provides evidence for the "Irrigation Jury", which implemented the "Mancha Oriental" pilot zone. This "Irrigation Jury" is a first instance court that tries to resolve mainly cases in which the authorised water abstraction has been exceeded, with a minimum of administrative procedure, and with the agreement of the parties. To do this, it uses a SPIDER_webGIS tool, integrated in the DIANA platform, which allows online access to the time series of images of the particular field.

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Table 4 - Products delivered to stakeholder, water managers and river basin authorities, submitted for validation.

PILOT AREAS, SPAIN	PRODUCTS DELIVERED TO WATER MANAGERS and THE RIVER BASIN AUTHORITIES 2016-2018				
	EO BASIC PRODUCTS Time series			Maps of Irrigated areas 2017 -2019	EO-based Soil Water Balance
	RGB	NDVI	Kcb		Net (Gross) Irrigation Water Requirements Monthly/annual)
Tierra del Vino	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bajo Jalón	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Bembezard MD	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mancha Oriental	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Figure 9 shows a real case brought to this “Irrigation Jury”. EO time series provides evidence for a field where several growth cycles appear corresponding to the subsequent implantation of a lettuce crop, while only one cycle permit was available. In many cases, the evidence provided by EO time series is clear and facilitates the resolution of the conflict.

Figure 9 – The time series displayed using the webGIS SPIDER_ERMOT tool provides evidence of the existence of several growth cycles in a plot where a lettuce crop is growing, while only one cycle authorization was available. This tool is used in the Irrigation Jury implemented in La Mancha Oriental.

3.2 Validation of technical quality: accuracy of the maps of irrigated areas and NIWR map

Field inspections in the case of the area of the Mancha Oriental have allowed evaluating the reliability of this methodology of crop classification, reaching an overall accuracy 90-95% in the case of the determination of irrigated areas of arable crops, and 70% in the case of the determination of irrigated areas of permanent crops like vineyard, olive and almond.

Field inspection for validating the maps of irrigated area has been performed during the three years in La Mancha Oriental area. Figure 10 shows an accuracy report (in Spanish) for the year 2017; similar figures can be found in similar reports for other years.

A comparison between the remote sensing-based classification and field information also was carried out in the Bajo Jalón pilot area. The required fieldwork was performed by the Ebro River Basin Authority (Confederación Hidrográfica del Ebro, In Spanish) in three municipalities Cariñena, Alfamen and Aguarón, with a total of 437 plots and 984 ha. In this case, approximately half of the area compared is destined for the vineyard

Results showed in Table 5 and Table 6 confirm that there are good agreements between the information provided by remote sensing procedure and the field inspections.

A summary of results about the reliability of EO for mapping irrigated areas is:

- EO mapping of irrigated areas is a mature and operative technique, widely accepted, even by court.
- Sentinel 2 imagery offers unprecedented spatial resolution and revisit time.
- Users require mapping irrigated areas several times during the growing season for supporting field work. [field work is currently needed for sanctioning an irrigated field without water rights].
- Mediterranean permanent crops like grapes, olive, almond, among others, challenge the current EO system for differentiating irrigated and non-irrigated areas.
- EO time series of images integrated into the webGIS platform provide evidences for Irrigation Jury.

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		CONTROL DE LA PRECISIÓN DE LA CLASIFICACIÓN DE RESUMEN ERMOT 2017			
Nombre clasificación:	clas2017_3c_epsg25830.tif				
Nombre datos de referencia:	Muestra_validacion				
Fecha datos de referencia:	27/10/2017				
Origen datos de referencia:	CHJ				
Tasa de muestreo:	31,07%				
Distribución de la muestra	61,05% Primavera; 20,71% Verano; 18,24% Prim.-Ver				
Matriz de contingencia					
	Campo				
	VERANO (1)	PRIMAVERA (2)	DOBLES COSECHAS (3)	Total ha.	
REGADÍO VERANO (1)	4.927,80	295,43	166,03	5.389,25	
REGADÍO PRIMAVERA (2)	99,10	15.576,13	34,82	15.710,05	
REGADÍO DOBLES COSECHAS (3)	466,65	326,61	4.638,95	5.432,21	
Total ha.	5.493,55	16.198,16	4.839,81	26.531,52	
Precisión de Identificación					
	Campo				
	VERANO (1)	PRIMAVERA (2)	DOBLES COSECHAS (3)	Total	
REGADÍO VERANO (1)	91,44	5,48	3,08	100	
REGADÍO PRIMAVERA (2)	0,63	99,15	0,22	100	
REGADÍO DOBLES COSECHAS (3)	8,59	6,01	85,40	100	
Precisión Cartográfica					
	Campo				
	VERANO (1)	PRIMAVERA (2)	DOBLES COSECHAS (3)		
REGADÍO VERANO (1)	89,70	1,82	3,43		
REGADÍO PRIMAVERA (2)	1,80	96,16	0,72		
REGADÍO DOBLES COSECHAS (3)	8,49	2,02	95,85		
Total	100	100	100		
Precisión global: 94,77					
Observaciones: Los cultivos asignados a cada grupo de campo han sido asignados según los criterios de cultivos establecidos por CHJ.					

Figure 10 – An accuracy report (in Spanish) for the year 2017 for the crop classification of ERMOT.

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Table 5 - Comparison between DIANA classification by Remote Sensing (RS) versus field work.

Surface (all the parcels -437-)					
				FIELD	
			Irrigated	Non irrigated	TOTAL (ha)
			1	2	
RS	Irrigated	1	202,76	75,74	278,50
	Non irrigated	2	57,12	647,95	705,07
TOTAL (ha)			259,88	723,69	983,57
Sample distribution			26,42	73,58	100,00

Surface (all the parcels -437-)					
				FIELD	
			Irrigated	Non irrigated	TOTAL (ha)
			1	2	
RS	Regadío	1	78,02	10,47	
	Secano	2	21,98	89,53	
TOTAL (ha)			100,00	100,00	
Global Accuracy			86,49		

Table 6 - Comparison for the vineyard classification (irrigated and non-irrigated) by remote sensing (RS) versus field work.

Surface (only vineyard -242-)					
				FIELD	
			Irrigated	Non irrigated	TOTAL (ha)
			1	2	
RS	Irrigated	1	193,06	38,81	231,87
	Non irrigated	2	19,69	173,80	193,49
TOTAL (ha)			212,75	212,61	425,36
Sample distribution			50,02	49,98	100,00

Surface (only vineyard -242-)					
				FIELD	
			Irrigated	Non irrigated	TOTAL (ha)
			1	2	
RS	Irrigated	1	90,75	18,25	
	Non irrigated	2	9,25	81,75	
TOTAL (ha)			100,00	100,00	
Global Accuracy			86,25		

Net Irrigation Water Requirement

Numerous works support the EO-based soil water balance for the calculation of the NIWR maps at field scale (for a review, see Calera et al., 2017)¹⁴. The so calculated NIWR represents the optimal amount of water to supply the crop demand. However, individual decisions made by farmers about the water to apply may not match this amount. But, the so calculated optimal amount of water to supply to the crop currently is being used for advising about water to apply in sustainable water use, taking into account that the procedure here used is the well-known FAO56 approach, in which we integrate the reflectance-based basal crop coefficient.

Table 7 shows a summary of the results achieved in the Spanish pilot areas.

Table 7 - Net Irrigation Water Requirement, NIWR, values in m³/ha for crop groups with the purpose of comparison between different years and different areas (Spanish pilot areas).

Land use irrigated areas	MANCHA ORIENTAL					TIERRA DEL VINO			
	2016	2017	2018	2019	Land use Average	2016	2017	2018	Land use Average
Spring (Wheat, Garlic,...)	3.200	3.400	2.600	3.500	3.160	2.200	3.200	2.100	2.400
Summer (Corn, Onion, ...)	5.000	5.200	4.400	4.600	4.800	5.200	5.300	4.800	5.120
Spring – Summer (alfalfa,...)	7.200	7.700	6.200	6.900	7.050	6.300	7.100	6.500	6.620
Grapes	1.400	1.200	1.000	1.200	1.220	1.200	1.300	1.200	1.230
Olive	2.000	1.600	1.400	1.600	1.610	-	-	-	-
Fruit	-	3.900	3.400	3.100	3.450	-	5.500	4.200	4.940
Nuts (almond, pistachios, nut)	-	2.200	2.400	2.600	2.400	-	2.500	2.700	2.600
Total Average	3.430	3.740	2.910	3.440	3.370	3.580	4.360	3.180	3.670

Land use irrigated areas	BAJO JALÓN				Land use irrigated areas	BEMBEZAR		
	2016	2017	2018	Land use Average		2018	2019	Average
Spring (Wheat, Garlic,...)	2.400	3.200	2.200	2.620	Herbaceous	2.893	4.663	3.778
Summer (Corn, Onion, ...)	4.900	4.900	4.500	4.790	Citrus	3.494	5.884	4.689
Spring – Summer (alfalfa,...)	6.900	7.200	5.700	6.570	-	-	-	-
Grapes	1.600	1.200	1.200	1.330	-	-	-	-
Olive	2.200	2.200	1.900	2.100	Olive	3.046	5.531	4.289
Fruit	-	6.600	5.000	5.800	Fruit trees	2.754	4.552	3.653
Nuts (almond, pistachios, nut)	-	3.200	3.100	3.150	Almond trees	2.012	4.054	3.033
Total Average	4.140	4.200	3.400	3.920	Average	2.840	4.937	3.888

¹⁴ Calera, A., Garrido-Rubio, J., Belmonte, M., Arellano, I., Fraile, L., Campos, I., Osann, A. (2017). Remote sensing-based water accounting to support governance for groundwater management for irrigation in La Mancha Oriental Acquirer, Spain. WIT Transactions on Ecology and the Environment, 220, 119-126.

The determination of RS-based NIWR is an indirect estimate of the amount of water to be applied under management conditions that are considered optimal. It is, therefore, an approximation to the amount of water actually applied as long as it is assumed that the individual decision of the water to be applied follows the agronomic patterns to obtain the greatest benefit using the water in a manner appropriate to the crop demand. However, individual decisions may be influenced by other variables, such as water availability, opportunity and cost in their use, personal experience and even personal appraisals. All this introduces a significant margin of uncertainty between the estimated value and the actual value of the water applied. Our preliminary results indicate that multi-year estimates can provide robust values to approach the average water doses that each crop requires.

A recently published work¹⁵ evaluates individual irrigation decisions - applied water - against estimated irrigation water requirements using a model very similar to the one applied here, for 1400 plots over a 13-year period in Nebraska (USA); in its conclusions it indicates the reliability of the model in aggregated data in large areas, highlighting the variability in the water applied to the modelled water demand, as a consequence of the individual irrigation behaviour of the farmers. Environmental factors, as if the year is wet or dry, overlap differences associated with different types of soils and others associated with the behaviour of farmer groups.

Beyond the mentioned aspects, the delivered NIWR maps are being checked directly by the users. The Water Directorate of Spanish Environmental Ministry has begun a program to evaluate the results obtained in DIANA, by comparing the NIWR maps against data directly obtained by the river basin authorities from water meter data, and other sources, in different areas and different environments. This program aims to evaluate the application of the same and homogeneous EO-based methodology and its potential use for the whole Spanish territory.

The use of the model presented in this paper to approximate the applied water will require further research that collects detailed information on farmer individual behaviour and its patterns. Selected water counter devices adequately operated and maintained, together with models such as the used in this work, may provide in the next future the knowledge and experience necessary to operate hybrid remote sensing-water meter systems for both water management and water accounting.

¹⁵ T Foster, I Z Gonçalves, I Campos, C M U Neale and N Brozović, 2019. Assessing landscape scale heterogeneity in irrigation water use with remote sensing and in situ monitoring. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 14 024004 <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/aaf2be>

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A relevant intermediate step ahead for remote sensing-based water accounting has been taken in La Mancha Oriental, MO, driven by the advances made in this project and recent challenges water manager face in the last years. In this pilot area, the irrigation water consumption can be estimated either by means of counters or by using the multi-year average value of the crop irrigation water requirement. The election of the system is at the farmer's choice, and usually farmers choose the multiyear average. This model exhibited a very satisfactory performance for water management, according to the farmers themselves and water authorities, and has achieved a successful recovery of groundwater piezometric levels. However, the rapid growth of new permanent crops, such as almond trees, has seriously jeopardized the application of this model. Until a few years ago, the most permanent crop in MO has been the vineyard. The multi-annual average water allocation for this crop adjust to the management of the vineyard, which requires apply deficit irrigation to achieve a product of enough quality. On the contrary, the yield of the almond tree crop is proportional to the water applied, until the water supply allows the transpiration of the canopy to reach its potential value. This potential value depends of each field, accordingly its green vegetation fraction, together with the atmospheric demand. Assigning the same water allocation to all almond tree plantations entailed significant errors and comparative grievances.

The solution adopted by the Assembly of farmers, that has become a legal rule in the Annual Exploitation Plan¹⁶, has been to assign different water endowment values according to the value reached by the NDVI of the fields in the months of July and August. The canopy of these almond crops, like that of other woody ones, exhibits a plateau at that time, with a value that is remarkably constant once the trees reach maturity. The decision to link average multiannual water consumption to the plateau NDVI value of each field is supported by the findings made within the framework of DIANA project. As an example, Figure 11 shows the plateau described by the NDVI time series for an almond tree crop in Albacete, Spain.

¹⁶ <http://www.dipualba.es/bop/ficheros/2018/139/BOP%20139-18-P-3.PDF>. (In Spanish)

Figure 11 – Ruling for water consumption based on plateau NDVI value in La Mancha Oriental. It shows the NDVI time series for a field of almond tree in Albacete (Spain), exhibiting the typical plateau, with NDVI value around 0.57. This value is used as water consumption indicator in the current Annual Exploitation Plan.

As a summary of the lessons learned about RS-based NIWR

- EO mapping of Net Irrigation Water Requirement is giving the first steps into its operational application.
- EO-based NIWR accounting requires coexisting with traditional local approaches, to which the EO must support and demonstrate the improvements achieved, such as transparency and equity, among others.
- Some easy to explain, easy to implement initiatives, such as **linking NIWR to the NDVI value** achieved by certain crop canopies are very relevant steps ahead.
- Further research is needed to deal with water stress, Regulated Deficit Irrigation.

3.3 Bembezar Margen Derecha pilot area

Maps of irrigated areas

Feragua represents 70 Water Users Associations (WUA) of Andalucía, 300.000 ha and around 30% of the irrigable land of the Guadalquivir Valley. Bembezar Margen Derecha Pilot is located in the mid Guadalquivir Valley and its Water Users Association belongs to FERAGUA. It was selected for DIANA project due to its important citrus production, modernized irrigation facilities and systems and its advanced management.

The Bembézar MD pilot area (37° 40' N, 5° 24' W) extends along the right bank of the Guadalquivir river from Palma del Río (Córdoba) to Lora del Río (Sevilla) (Figure 12). It covers 12000 ha of irrigated land and encompasses 1200 owners. The average size of the plots is 7 ha, however the average irrigable surface

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per owner is 10 ha. The zone is divided into eleven sectors (Figure 12) The irrigation scheme occupies part of the alluvial plain of the Guadalquivir river and the soils are mainly fluvisols and cambisols.

Figure 12 – Management scheme of the WUA Bembezar Margen Derecha

Main crops in Bembezar are presented in the following table:

Table 8 - Main crops grown in Bembezar

Crop	Area (ha)	Crop	Area (ha)
Orange trees > 8 years	3127	Onion	113
Maize	2613	Water melon	110
Orange trees < 8 years	2346	Alfalfa	96
Cotton	935	Vegetable gardens	90
Wheat	704	Tomato	62
Sunflower	484	Melon	50
Fruit trees	393	Potato	47
Olives	288	Persimmon	33
Fallow	172	Almond trees	30
Faba beans	119	Oat + barley	19

The perimeter of the WUA is very well defined. The farmers within the perimeter have water right associated to the land they own. The maps used by the WUA are cadastral maps and are presented here.

Figure 13 – Map of irrigated areas of Bembezar Pilot

Crop Classification maps

Crop classification maps were obtained from the SIGPAC the geographical information system that identifies farms declared by farmers and is actualized every year.

Figure 14 – Crop classification maps of Bembezar Pilot

Table 9 - Evolution of surface in main permanent crop types of Bembezar pilot from 2017 to 2019

Land use percentage of Bembezar				
Crop classification	2017	2018	2019	Area 2019
Citrus crops	49.1%	53.7%	54.8%	6144 ha
Olive trees	4.3%	6.3%	7.2%	760 ha
Nut trees	1.7%	2.6%	3.1%	228 ha
Fruit trees	2.9%	- 2.1%	- 1.6%	415 ha

Crop Evapotranspiration maps

For calculating crop evapotranspiration for Bembezar Pilot, a methodology based on local knowledge of the Guadalquivir basin (Mateos *et al.*, 2013) and used by the Water Authorities of the river basin was used in order to harmonize works that are being developed in the Guadalquivir river basin. The procedure for calculating ETc from remote sensing tools is described below:

$$ET = K_c * ET_o \quad (1)$$

Where:

- ET_o measured at weather stations

$$K_c = K_{c, \text{bare soil}} + (1 - K_{c, \text{bare soil}})K_{cb} \quad \text{if } K_{cb} < 1, \quad (2)$$

$$K_c = 1 + \frac{K_{c, mx} - 1}{K_{cb, mx} - 1} (K_{cb} - 1) \quad \text{if } K_{cb} \geq 1, \quad (3)$$

An approach of K_{cb} based on vegetation index, concretely NDVI. Considering that the vegetation index is sensitive and linearly related to the fraction of ground cover,

$$f_c = \frac{NDVI - NDVI_{mn}}{NDVI_{mx} - NDVI_{mn}} \quad (4)$$

$$K_{cb} = \min \left[K_{cb, mx}, \frac{K_{cb, mx}}{f_{c, mx}} \left(\frac{NDVI - NDVI_{mn}}{NDVI_{mx} - NDVI_{mn}} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

where $f_{c, mx}$, $NDVI_{mn}$, $NDVI_{mx}$ are taken from Table 10 and f_c is calculated as:

$$f_c = \frac{NDVI - NDVI_{mn}}{NDVI_{mx} - NDVI_{mn}} \quad (6)$$

Table 10 - Seasonal K_c , bare soil

K_c , bare soil	Autumn	0.8
	Winter	0.8
	Spring	0.6
	Summer	0.0

Table 11 - f_c, mx , $NDVI_{mn}$, $NDVI_{mx}$ for different crops

Crop	$K_{cb, mx}$	$K_{c, mx}$	$f_{c, mx}$	$NDVI_{mx}$	$NDVI_{mn}$
Citrus	0.75	0.85	0.70	0.9	0.13
Olive	0.70	0.85	0.70	0.7	0.13
Fruit trees	1.00	1.10	0.70	0.9	0.13
Cotton	1.15	1.20	0.80	0.9	0.13
Wheat	1.10	1.15	0.80	0.9	0.13
Sunflower	1.10	1.15	0.80	0.9	0.13
Corn	1.15	1.20	0.80	0.9	0.13
Alfalfa	1.15	1.20	0.80	0.9	0.13
Sugarbeet	1.15	1.20	0.80	0.9	0.13
Tomato	1.10	1.15	0.80	0.9	0.13
Potato	1.10	1.15	0.80	0.9	0.13

The same methodology was used for 2017, 2018 and 2019. Details of 2019 are presented here: NDVI was obtained from 34 images with cloud cover less than 20% from the Satellites Sentinel 2A and Sentinel 2B and for the cropping season 2018 – 2019. ET was calculated daily and the results were aggregated monthly and annually following DIANA products structure.

Table 12 - DIANA products structure for Bembezar Pilot

Tile	Granule	n° S2 images per month	Acquisition Time (yyyy-mm-dd)
T30	STG	1	2018/09/29
		3	2018/10/09-24-29
		1	2018/11/28
		1	2018/12/28
		3	2019/01/07-12-27
		2	2019/02/06-26
		3	2019/03/03-18-28
		2	2019/04/12-22
		3	2019/05/02-12-27
		3	2019/06/06-11-21
		5	2019/07/01-11-16-21-31
		2	2019/08/10-28
		4	2019/09/09-19-24-29

Information was sent to the manager of the WUA monthly for joint validation between the WUA and Feragua using DIANA platform.

Net irrigation water requirements map

Monthly Net irrigation Water Requirements were calculated subtracting monthly precipitation from monthly ET. Information was aggregated to annual values and maps in order to evaluate the obtained data. Main results of annual Net Irrigation Requirements per crops are presented in the following table:

Table 13 - Net Irrigation Requirements per crop and year for Bembezar Pilot

Crop classification	Net Irrigation Water Requirements average (m3/ha/year)			
	2017	2018	2019	Average
Citrus	4129	4544	5884	4852
Olive	4586	3575	5531	4564
Fruit trees	4093	2570	4552	3738
Nut trees	3392	3912	4054	3786
Herbaceous	4817	3688	4663	4389
Average	4203	3658	4937	

These differences between years was due to the variable precipitation of the Guadalquivir River basin where periods of drought are cyclical. Annual precipitation for the study years were: 680 mm in 2017, 611 mm in 2018 and 383 mm for 2019; apart from that, precipitation distribution was very irregular. All climatic characteristics described have a clear reflection on the obtained values for Net Irrigation Water Requirements as presented in Figure 15.

Figure 15 – Monthly Net Irrigation Requirements and precipitation for 2017, 2018 and 2019

It was noticed that ETo values slightly increased for 2019 as compared with previous years, being the most representative change during May 2019 as shown in the following table.

Table 14 - Monthly evolution of ETo in Bembezar for 2017, 2018 and 2019.

ETo	2017	2018	2019
October	81.8	107.12	80.35
November	38.2	52.31	33.29
December	34.0	71.36	70.39
January	37.6	35.66	37.61
February	44.4	51.08	55.47
March	86.0	70.98	98.99
April	128.8	109.52	109.19
May	157.8	137.52	183.15
June	211.9	177.1	196.2
July	206.1	203.5	208.73
August	181.6	189.56	191.51
September	134.5	137.5	129.53
TOTAL	1343	1343	1394

To assess the performance of irrigation in the area, the Relative Irrigation Supply (RIS) indicator was applied for 2019 in the Bembezar Pilot area.

$$RIS = \frac{\text{Applied water (m}^3\text{)}}{NIWR \text{ (Remote Sensing)}} \quad (7)$$

Where RIS > 1 means over irrigation and RIS < 1 deficit irrigation.

Applied water measured at hydrant level was provided by the WUA and analyzed for 2019.

Figure 16 – NIWR for the period 01/10/2018 to 30/09/2019 of the Pilot Bembezar

RIS index was calculated for 2019 by taking into account total water measured at hydrant and the estimation of Net Irrigation Water Requirements as previously described using remote sensing tools. The result is presented below:

$$RIS\ 2017 = \frac{3786\ m^3}{4461\ m^3} = 0.84 \quad (8)$$

$$RIS\ 2018 = \frac{3337\ m^3}{4085\ m^3} = 0.82 \quad (9)$$

$$RIS\ 2019 = \frac{4009\ m^3}{4936\ m^3} = 0.82 \quad (10)$$

Due to the differences in precipitation between the study years, applied water and net irrigation requirements varied, however RIS was almost the same.

During 2019 precipitation was less (383 mm) compared with the 611 mm of 2018, and farmers were very conscious of the situation of water scarcity so in many cases started to apply deficit irrigation methods in order to accomplish water allocation and save some water for the following irrigation season in case water availability would not improve. So it can be said that water was used according to the hydrological situation of the Bembezar area and slightly under crop irrigation water requirements as shown by the RIS value.

4 Romanian Pilot area: Data products validation for year 2019

The validation approach require ground measurements of the soil moisture gathering in the same time with Sentinel-1 satellite passage. The main difficulty of the validation procedure consisted in location of the Banat test area (shown in Fig. 16), one measurement campaign being performed on 25th of May. This campaign could not be considered enough for soil moisture validation. Analyzing vegetation indices, soil type and rainfall regime that influences the ground water level to increase near the land surface (ranging between 0.4 – 4m), overestimated values of the volumetric soil moisture were obtained.

Table 15 - Banat pilot area: main crops in 2019 and data needs.

Crop type	Plot dimension (ha)	EO data	Meteo data	Observation period
Sunflower	192	Sentinel1 Sentinel 2	Precipitation, Temperature, ETP	March- September
Maize	630.1			
Winter wheat	395			
Alfalfa	24.8			

A total of 34 Sentinel-1 data covering January 2019 – September 2019 were prepared for supervised classification by applying special processing steps like: orbit corrections, radiometric calibration, speckle filtering, terrain correction and normalisation. Machine learning algorithms results are shown in Table 16

Table 16 - Machine learning classification results

Machine Learning Algorithm	Crop type	Accuracy	Correct predictions	Bias
Random forest	Sunflower, winter wheat, maize, alfalfa	0.99	60.61	-21.16
K-Nearest Neighbor Classification ¹⁷ (KNN)	Sunflower, winter wheat, maize, alfalfa	0.99	63.13	-7.5
Minimum Distance Classifier (MD)	Sunflower, winter wheat, maize, alfalfa	0.99	51.93	3.71

¹⁷Campos, Guilherme O.; Zimek, Arthur; Sander, Jörg; Campello, Ricardo J. G. B.; Micenková, Barbora; Schubert, Erich; Assent, Ira; Houle, Michael E. (2016). On the evaluation of unsupervised outlier detection: measures, datasets, and an empirical study. Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery. doi:10.1007/s10618-015-0444-8. ISSN 1384-5810

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A simple threshold algorithm was applied on 37 Sentinel 2 data covering March to August 2019 period for irrigated areas classification. A logical operation ($NDVI > 0.7$) was applied on NDVI images to differentiate the irrigated areas from the non-irrigated lands. The result is depicted in Figure 17.

Figure 17 – Distribution of irrigated crops in Banat pilot.

4.1 Crop water requirements 2018-2019

In order to estimate the ETC (crop water requirements) for 2018 and 2019 NDVI values were calculated using Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 cloud free images and atmospherically corrected.

Since year 2017, Agrisat Web GIS online platform was updated. Now the platform has a new, more user friendly interface. In addition, new tools were added in order to enhance the capabilities of data visualization and on the fly analysis. Vegetation curves were obtained for all the pilot parcels.

Figure 18 – Updated AgriSat platform

After consulting the online platform, a number of 24 images was selected in order to calculate the ETC for 2018. For 2019 the same procedure was used, with a total of 13 Sentinel-2 images.

The crop water requirements products were processed using TONI pbp software, provided by UCLM. The software automatically interpolates the gaps between the missing images and by doing so, it completes the vegetation curve with NDVI values for each day. The results are rasters with crop water requirements for every pixels. Below are depicted the crop water requirements for 2018 and 2019 side by side.

Figure 19 – ETP estimated for 2018 and 2019

4.2 Net Irrigation Water Requirements for 2018 and 2019

According to the definition, net irrigation water requirement (NIWR) has been calculated by subtracting the effective rainfall (PP) from crop evatranspiration (ETc).

$$\text{NIWR} = \text{ETc} - \text{PP} \quad (\text{mm}) \quad (11)$$

To this end, data regarding the precipitation and crop growing period have been collected. Following table show the data for each crop.

Table 17 - 2018 crops and their vegetation period

Group	Precipitation (mm)	Start. Date	Finish. Date
Alfalfa	330	29/04/2018	28/08/2018
Maize south	229	29/05/2018	30/08/2018
Maize north	248	21/05/2018	31/08/2018
Sorghum	244	27/05/2018	21/08/2018
Soybeans	244	27/05/2018	17/08/2018
Wheat	416	17/10/2017	01/07/2018

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Table 18 - 2019 crops and their vegetation period

Group	Precipitation (mm)	Start. Date	Finish. Date
Maize	300	11/05/2019	18/08/2019
Sunflower	302	09/05/2019	18/08/2019
Wheat	267	22/02/2019	01/07/2019

Following figures show the NIWR for each parcel and for different crop in the investigate period (NIWR is estimated in millimeter)

Figure 20 – Average NIWR (label) in mm north parcels 2019

Figure 21 – Average NIWR (label) north parcels 2018

Figure 22 – Average NIWR (label) south parcels 2019

Figure 23 – Average NIWR (label) south parcels 2018

4.3 Gross Irrigation Water Requirements (mm) (NIWR/€)

Finally, the Gross Irrigation Water Requirement (GIWR) has been calculated by applying the efficiency of the irrigation system at farm scale which ranging from 0.8 to 0.9. The results have been validated by SC Emiliana West Rom, also providing the information related to irrigation water volume for a sample of selected parcels.

Figure 24 – Average GIWR (label) in mm north parcels 2019

Figure 25 – Average GIWR (label) north parcels 2018

Figure 26 – Average GIWR (label) south parcels 2019

Figure 27 – Average GIWR (label) south parcels 2018

5 Diana benchmarking

Diana Benchmarking aims to apply innovative techniques to resolve open issues raised from the work carried out along with final user partners of the consortium. The activity wasn't planned in the DIANA project at proposal stage. It is mainly focused to the application of different modelling to improve the detection of irrigated areas and the estimation of crop water requirement for crops managed in condition of water deficit. In detail, more attention has been dedicated to tree crops. The need arises from the growing surface of tree crops registered in Europe in the recent years. In the Figure 28, are reported in **thousand hectares** the areas of all fruit trees (in particular apples, pears and cherries), all nut trees, berry plantations (except strawberries), citrus fruit trees, vineyards, olive trees and other permanent crops used for human consumption¹⁸.

Figure 28 – Permanent crops for human consumption by area in Europe (2018)

The increase of the tree crops has been confirmed also by farmers in the different DIANA's pilot areas, and especially by water managers, who put an interesting question during the DIANA meetings:

“How DIANA works to discriminate irrigated and not-irrigated tree crops?”

¹⁸ EUROSTAT database: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/>

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As reported in the paragraph 2.1, the detection process of the irrigated areas is based on the basic assumption that the hydrologic deficit typical of the semi-arid environments, as for the Mediterranean basin, the only vigorous crops are those that are irrigated. However, this approach is very suitable for distinguishing irrigated herbaceous crop from rainfed crops (Figure 29).

Figure 29 – Temporal variability of NDVI for irrigated and rainfed crops.

Diversely the proposed approach might fail in distinguishing irrigated tree crops from the not-irrigated tree crop. In the following graphs, extracted from the dataset 2019 collected in the Sannio Alifano pilot area, there are significant differences in terms of NDVI trend between rainfed and maize plot (Figure 29), while for the irrigated and not irrigated hazelnut such differences are negligible (Figure 30).

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Figure 30 – Temporal NDVI (in green) and precipitation profiles (in blue) irrigated and not-irrigated parcels in the Sannio Alifano districts.

In other words, following the above-mentioned paradigm based on VIS-NIR, each parcel detected with tree crop was labelled as irrigated, with the relative overestimation of the irrigated areas and water abstractions amount. For this purpose, the VIS-NIR-SWIR and radar domain has been explored by using the OPTRAM model and TU Wien algorithm, in order to improve the discrimination of the irrigated and not irrigated areas. The theoretical aspects and the results achieved are reported in the following subsections.

5.1 OPTRAM

Background

Sadeghi et al., (2017)¹⁹ proposed a physical “Optical TRapezoid Model” (OPTRAM) to remote sensing of soil moisture (SM) EO data.

OPTRAM is based on the pixel distribution within the shortwave infrared transformed reflectance (STR)-Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) space (STR-NDVI space), defined as:

$$STR = \frac{(1 - R_{SWIR})^2}{2R_{SWIR}} \quad (12)$$

$$W = \frac{\theta}{\theta_s} = \frac{i_d + s_d \cdot NDVI - STR}{i_d - i_w + (s_d - s_w) \cdot NDVI} \quad (13)$$

$$STR_d = i_d + s_d \cdot NDVI \quad (14)$$

$$STR_w = i_w + s_w \cdot NDVI \quad (15)$$

$$W = \frac{STR - STR_d}{STR_w - STR_d} \quad (16)$$

Figure 31 – Sketch illustrating parameters of the optical trapezoid model.

The advantage of the STR- θ space over the conventional triangle/trapezoid approach (LST- θ space) (Carlson et al., 1994)²⁰ is that it only requires optical data and it can be universally parameterised for a

¹⁹ Sadeghi, M., Babaeian, E., Tuller, M., Jones, S. B. (2017). The optical trapezoid model: A novel approach to remote sensing of soil moisture applied to Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 observations. *Remote sensing of environment*, 198, 52-68.

²⁰ Carlson, T. N., Gillies, R. R., Perry, E. M. (1994). A method to make use of thermal infrared temperature and NDVI measurements to infer surface soil water content and fractional vegetation cover. *Remote sensing reviews*, 9(1-2), 161-173.

given location because STR- θ is not affected by ambient atmospheric factors. However, the STR- θ space is sensitive to oversaturated pixels (due to ponding water), and then, occasionally, the index W assumes values higher than 1 (Sadeghi et al., 2017)¹⁹.

This section aims to show the testing of the optical trapezoidal model (OPTRAM) for the remote sensing monitoring of soil moisture, at high resolution, for detection of irrigated crop.

Italian Pilot area

For the Italian Pilot area, the capabilities of the OPTRAM model were evaluated with aim to distinguish the irrigated and not irrigated tree crop. The analysis was conducted at district and parcel scale.

District scale

To improving the detection of irrigated tree crop, the OPTRAM model has been applied and incorporated within the processing chain for irrigated area detection. By considering both irrigated and not irrigated plots with tree crops in the Italian Pilot area, a prolonged period without rainfall were identified during the irrigation season 2019 which coincides with the first three weeks of August. It was selected for the analysis, considering its length and the high values of ETo (red box in Figure 32); the other two dry periods (not filled red box) were not considered because either too short either too close to rainy days. The values for STR (Eq.12) and NDVI were computed from nine S2 images collected during the dry period in August; their distribution within the STR(NDVI) scatterplot is shown in Figure 33.a. In this scatterplot the upper limit represents the position of pixels corresponding to wet conditions in the soil-plant ensemble (“wet edge”), the lower the drier (“dry edge”).

Figure 32 – Identification of dry periods for the setup of the OPTRAM algorithm, Sannio Alifano districts.

Successively, the region between the two extreme edges, was divided in four sub-sections (Figure 33.b) and an occurrence analysis was carried out for the pixels corresponding to tree crop by counting the number of times (for each of the 9 images of the dry period) each pixel was found within the upper wet regions of the scatterplot in Figure 33.b. Only pixels with a zero frequency (in Figure 34.a) – hence falling within the dry part of the scatterplot- were considered NOT IRRIGATED and a new thematic class in the map of irrigated areas has been created (Figure 34.b).

Figure 33 – STR-NDVI scatterplot and subdivision of wet and dry regions- OPTRAM algorithm, Sannio Alifano districts

Figure 34 – a) Occurrence analysis of wet pixels; b) final map, Sannio Alifano districts

Evaluation at the parcel scale

The OPTRAM model was evaluated for a sample of 35 parcels of hazelnut tree under irrigated and not irrigated conditions (Figure 35).

Figure 35 – Evaluation of OPTRAM in hazelnut parcels, Sannio Alifano district.

As was done at the district scale, also in this case, the OPTRAM model was derived considering the S2 images acquired during the dry period in August 2019, but in order to define a more accurate parameterisation, new wet and dry edges were delineated, plotting in the STR-NDVI space only the pixel of the investigated Hazelnut parcels (*Figure 36*).

Figure 36 – STR-NDVI scatterplot for the hazelnut parcels.

This approach leads to mapping the relative soil saturation index (W) for each S2 image during the dry period accordingly to Eq.16, as originally proposed by Sadeghi et al. (2017). An example of the procedure to distinguish irrigated and not irrigated tree crop is shown in Figure 34 and 35 for two plots used as test case. The first one is declared irrigated (*Figure 37*) and the second one not irrigated (*Figure 38*): The trend pattern of W index is able to explain with evidence the difference between the irrigated and not-irrigated hazelnut parcels.

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Figure 37 – Relative saturation index W (Eq.16) for an irrigated hazelnut parcel.

Figure 38 – Relative saturation index W (Eq.16) for a NOT irrigated hazelnut parcel.

In the first case, the irrigated hazelnut parcel shows a higher amplitude of W trend, with values never below to 0.4 and with four peaks close or upper to 0.6, related to the irrigation events.

Diversely, the not-irrigated hazelnut parcel shows a less amplitude of W trend than the previous case, with values ever below 0.4, confirming the absence of the irrigation events.

Other several test case which are not reported here have been checked during the dry period. In any case the results are very good and the developed technique can be considered suitable to the scope. Following other test cases for the other pilot are shown.

Spain-Bembezar (Feragua)

For Spanish pilot area of Bembezar (Cordova, Spain) a set of farms with different crop types have been selected for testing the OPTRAM algorithm (*Figure 39*). The collected data and information are reported in table 16. By analysing the records from the meteo stations located within the study area, a dry period (in absence of rainfall) of the three months (from June to August 2018) was identified.

By means of the procedure outlined for the Italian pilot area, a scatterplot of STR and NDVI values have been derived for the pixels of the selected farm parcels and the wet and dry edge were drawn (*Figure 40*).

Figure 39 – Distribution of crop type (irrigated) over Bembezar (Cordova, Spain) study area

Figure 40 – Distribution of the pixels in the OPTRAM (NDVI-STR) space based on n° 12 acquisitions dates of Sentinel-2 during the year 2018 in absence of rainfall. The parameterization coefficients: $i_w = 1.0$ (wet edge intercept), $s_w = 8.5$ (wet edge slope), $i_d = 0$ (dry edge intercept), and $s_d = 2.0$ (dry edge slope).

Figure 41 shows different irrigation management and consequently difference in applied water volume (as described in Table 16) which correspond to distinct trends of the STR throughout the considered period. Figure 38 left shows the trend of STR for two different points inside a parcel cultivate with maize (id 8 18). Figure 38 right shows the trend of STR for two different points inside a parcel cultivate with cotton (id 8.1.64). On the average, the increase of STR in the maize parcel (on the left of Figure 38) is explained by repetitive irrigation applications, differently from the cotton crop where irrigation is applied later during the same period. The intra-plot difference is explained due to differences in soil type or other not homogeneous inputs. Analogous differentiation can be observed for tree crops in Figure 39.

Figure 41 – Time series of STR for two point inside the parcel with maize (on the left) and two point inside the cotton parcel (on the right).

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Analogous differentiation in terms of STR can be observed for tree crops in Figure 42 for two parcels with citrus orchard where the applied water volume is different. The two parcels are both irrigated but the pattern trends of STR show a different water content which can refer to the higher volume applied for parcel id 3 (blue line).

Figure 42 – Time series of STR for two parcels with the same crop (citrus orchard), but with different magnitude of irrigation volume applied. For plot Id 3 (blue line) the applied volume is higher than plot id 5.64 (red line).

In more details, the graphs in Figure 43 shows more clearly the temporal variation of the relative saturation index W along with the corresponding NDVI, for the same two citrus plots. These results are in according to the information provided by water manager.

Figure 43 – Time series of NDVI (in green) and W (in blue) for the parcels with the same crop (citrus orchard), but with different irrigation distributed irrigation volumes.

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As matter of fact, the data provided by water manager point out that the parcel id=3 (Figure 43 left side) has been irrigated with 3.8 mm for 3.5 hours with a frequency of 5 day per week; meanwhile the irrigation applied to the parcel id=5-64 (Figure 43 right side) is smaller, corresponding to 1 to 3.1 mm, for 1-3 hours every day. Therefore, the OPTRAM model is able to highlight the differences in irrigation in the two cases.

Table 19 – Information for selected plots related to Spanish pilot area (Bembezár, Spain).

<i>Plot id</i>	<i>area (ha)</i>	<i>Use of the soil</i>	<i>Year of the plantation (tree crop) or Sowing date (Herbaceous crop)</i>	<i>Distance between trees</i>	<i>Distance between rows</i>	<i>Irrigation period</i>	<i>Hours of irrigation</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Dose per irrigation</i>	<i>flow rate</i>
3	17.77									
21	5.12		1959	5m	5m					
24	11.81	Orange orchard				From June to September	3.5 hours	5 days per week	3.8 mm	2.2 litre/hour
22	6.41		2016	5m	5m					
23	6.40		2012	5m	5m					
5-64	5.35 (3.12+2.23)	Orange orchard	2005	6m	5m	From May to September, from min to max values of irrigation applied	1 hour	Everyday	1.0 mm/day	2.3 litre/hour
	2.5 hours						Everyday	2.6 mm/day		
	3 hours						Everyday	3.1 mm/day		
6.1-3-48	22.13	Super intensive olive trees plantation	2003	1.5m	4.5m	During May and June irrigation	10 hours	2 days per week	6.8 mm	2.3 litre/hour
							11 hours		7.5 mm	
							12 hours		8.2 mm	
						During July and August	5 hours	3.4 mm		
11	9.33									
12	0.44		2012						4.6	
14	0.19	Orange orchard		6m	6m	From June to September	7 hours	7 days per week		1 litre/hour
13	3.05		2017						2.3	
15	2.17		2018						2.3	
8.1-81	6.5 (1.52+4.98)	Maize	March/early April in 2018 20-apr-19	NA	0.75m	-	24 hours	2-3 days	33.6 mm	2.1 litre/hour
8.1-64	4.77 (1.49+3.28)	Cotton	Late April/ early May	NA	0.95m	from June to August	24 hours	each 5 days	26.6 mm	2.1 litre/hour

La Mancha oriental – Spain

The OPTRAM model has been applied to 18 vineyard parcels falling within the borders of La Mancha Oriental. The test case parcels present different water management, either irrigated either not irrigated (Figure 44).

Figure 44 – Selected vineyard parcels irrigated (in blue) and not irrigated (in red) in La Mancha Oriental

As the previous test case, a dry period (April to August 2019) was selected considering the absence of rainfall (Figure 45). The OPTRAM model was derived considering sixteen S2 images acquired during the selected period. With aim to define a more accurate parameterisation, the wet and dry edges were

delineated in the STR-NDVI space only for the pixel of the investigated vineyard parcels. The corresponding parameters are also given in the caption of Figure 46.

Figure 45 – Identification of the dry period for the La Mancha Oriental.

Figure 46 - STR-NDVI scatterplot for the 18 vineyards parcels, La Mancha Oriental: $id=0$; $iw=0.9$; $sd=1.7$; $sw=1.4$

Similarly to the Sannio Alifano and Bembezar pilot area, there is a clear distinction in the temporal variability of the relative saturation index W between irrigated and not-irrigated vineyard parcels. In the first case, the irrigated vineyard parcel shows a higher amplitude of W trend, with values ranged between

0.2 to 0.8 while for the not-irrigated vineyard parcel shown a less amplitude of W trend than the previous case, with the values ever below 0.4, confirming the absence of the irrigation events (Figure 47).

Figure 47 - Time series of NDVI (in green) and W (in blue) for the parcels with the same crop (vineyard) under irrigated and not irrigated conditions.

Romania – Banat

For the Banat pilot area (Romania), as what was done for the Italian and Spanish pilot areas, the capabilities of the OPTRAM model to detect the irrigated and not irrigated crops at parcel scale were tested. In this case the analysis were performed on the herbaceous crop. In detail, the data set has included 15 parcels with irrigated maize and 85 parcels with not-irrigated soybean (Figure 48).

Figure 48 - Selected parcels, Banat, Romania

The OPTRAM model was applied by considering n.26 Sentinel-2 images from March to September 2019. With aim of determining more accurately the OPTRAM parameters, the wet and dry edges were identified by plotting only the pixels of the investigated maize and soybean parcels in the STR-NDVI space (Figure 49). The spatial distribution of the pixels in the STR-NDVI scatterplot is significantly different from those found in the previous pilot areas in Italy and Spain, due to wetter conditions compared to the other sites.

Figure 49 - STR-NDVI scatterplot derived from S2 acquisition during irrigation season 2019

In Figure 50, an example of two different trends of the relative saturation index W is shown, in order to highlight the difference between the irrigated maize (id 101, left side) and not-irrigated soybean parcel (id 112, right side).

In the first case, the maize field shows high values of W , in phase with the NDVI trend, while for the not-irrigated soybean parcel low values of W trend than the previous case is spotted. Besides, in the latter case the W trend has values ever below 0.4, confirming the absence of the irrigation events.

Figure 50 - Time series of NDVI (in green) and W (in blue) for the parcels in Banat, Romania, under irrigated and not irrigated conditions.

As a conclusion, we can affirm that the OPRAM model has demonstrated to be capable to distinguish the irrigated crop from not irrigated crop and the approach can be transferred to different geographical regions, with different crop types, climate and management. It confirms that additional information derived in the SWIR spectrum is valuable data source for improving irrigated area mapping in a variety of environmental conditions.

5.2 TU WIEN algorithm

Radar signal modelling

Change detection method developed by Wagner for soil moisture estimation at the global scale (1 Km resolution) using SAR scatterometer sensor was used for modelling backscattered radar signal over wheat and rapeseed^{21,22}. This method considers temporal stability of the spatial soil moisture pattern supposing soil roughness and vegetation conditions are not changed when a dense time series of SAR data is available. In a particular day, soil moisture is computing by comparing wetting and drying trend

²¹ Wagner, W. L. (1999). A study of vegetation cover effects on ERS scatterometer data. IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, 37 (2): 938-948.

²²Wagner, W. P. F. (2008). Temporal stability of soil moisture and radar backscatter observed by the Advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (ASAR). Sensors, (8): 1174-1197.

for radar backscattered signal using historically lowest and highest backscattered values as references (eq.17 – eq.19):

$$\sigma^o(\theta, t) = \sigma_{dry}^o(30) + \beta(\theta - 30) + Sm_s(t) \quad (17)$$

$$S = \sigma_{wet} - \sigma_{dry} \quad (18)$$

$$SM_t = \frac{\sigma^o(t) - \sigma_{dry}^o(30)}{\sigma_{wet}^o(30) - \sigma_{dry}^o(30)} \quad (19)$$

where,

- S is radar sensitivity,
- β is slope (local incidence angle),
- $m_s(t)$ is the surface soil moisture normalised at an incidence angle of 30°.

As a result, surface soil moisture is expressed in volumetric units (%) and scaled between zero and one. This method is applied only for positive temperature values when the soil is not covered with snow or is frozen.

Soil moisture retrieval

Soil moisture estimation implies calibration of the change detection method whose main steps are described as follows.

Step 1. Normalising the backscattering coefficients. To adjust local incidence variation during acquisition, VV and VH-polarized backscattered coefficients are normalised by using Lambert law from optics²³:

$$\sigma_{\theta_{ref}}^o = \sigma_{\theta}^o \frac{\cos^2 \theta_{ref}}{\cos^2 \theta} \quad (20)$$

where,

$\sigma_{\theta_{ref}}^o$ and σ_{θ}^o are backscattering coefficients observed at incidences angles θ and θ_{ref} . As is mentioned earlier, the incidence angle of Sentinel-1 data is set to 39°.

Step 2. Determine dry and wet references. After normalization and meteorological data analysis, the dry and wet references are determined by statistical methods of noise analysis.

Step 3. Calculate surface soil moisture. Soil moisture is estimated by applying Eq. 19, comparing reference backscattered signal with dry and wet references values.

²³Topouzelis, K. S. (2016). Incidence angle normalization of Wide Swath SAR data for oceanographic applications. Open Geosciences, 8(1), 450-464.

Step 4. Analyse the vegetation contribution to the soil moisture. The estimated soil moisture content values are used to model vegetation contribution and to validate the estimated results since no measurements have been done in the test area.

Surface soil moisture estimation

Investigations were focused on establishing the dry and wet references based on seasonal variation which reflect vegetation phenology. This variation can induce backscatter changes that required vegetation correction. Sentinel-1 data covering January 2019 - September 2019 were analysed separately to see the radar temporal response during the seeding and dormancy crop stages in correlation with precipitation and evapotranspiration values (Figure 51). The change detection algorithm was used to scale dry and wet references of the backscattering coefficients over the whole SAR datasets in order to estimate surface soil moisture (Figure 52).

Figure 51 - Rainfall regime (left side) and evapotranspiration (right side) in 2019 crop growing season

Figure 52 - Dry and wet reference characteristics to Banat pilot area.

Results

Sentinel-1 data were analyzed to estimate and assess the volumetric soil moisture. First, radar signal response to the soil moisture content was investigated on crop type. Secondly, correlations between estimated volumetric soil moisture, NDVI and CWC were examined since the NDVI is the most sensitive parameter for the accurate estimation of SSM. The results are depicted in the following figures for Winter wheat (Figure 53), Alfalfa (Figure 54), Maize (Figure 55), Sunflowers (Figure 56),

Figure 53 - Surface soil moisture for winter wheat (2019). A good correlation is obtained in both cases (VV and VH polarizations)

Figure 54 - Surface soil moisture for alfalfa. A good correlation is obtained in both cases (VV and VH polarizations)

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Figure 55 - Surface soil moisture for maize. A good correlation is obtained in both cases (VV and VH polarizations)

Figure 56 - Surface soil moisture for sunflower. A good correlation is obtained in both cases (VV and VH polarizations)

Time series of Sentinel-1 data for volumetric soil moisture estimation

The surface soil moisture estimations in DIANA projects are synthetise in the table below.

Table 20 - Soil moisture estimations using TU Wien algorithn

Crop type	2017		2018		2019	
	Correlation Sigma - SSM	Correlation SSM -NDVI	Correlation Sigma - SSM	Correlation SSM -NDVI	Correlation Sigma - SSM	Correlation SSM -NDVI
Winter wheat	0.78	0.65	x	x	0.8	0.1
Rapeseed	0.72	0.57	0.6	0.1	x	x
Soybeans	x	x	0.97	0.66	x	x
Maize	x	x	0.75	0.45	0.86	0.8
Sorghun	x	x	0.95	0.72	x	x
Sunflower	x	x	0.92	0.65	0.88	0.84
Alfalfa	x	x	0.7	0.2	0.8	0.3

Sentinel-1 data has been processing in ENVI SarScape 5.4 in order to reduce bias noise induced by the Sentinel-1 sensor.

6 Verification of the Meteorological Products

6.1 Introduction

Forecast verification is the process and practice of determining the quality of forecasts in the spatial and temporal domain²⁴. This section describes the methodology that followed to verify weather forecast fields and the gridded observational data produced by the statistical and dynamical downscaling processes during the project's 1st and 2nd pilot phases.

6.2 Data and Methods

For the verification of the meteorological parameters, the MET²⁵ code (Model Evaluation Tools) version 5.2 was used. MET is a collection of functions written in C that was developed by the Developmental Testbed Center to provide to the atmospheric community highly configurable and state-of-the-art verification tools. These tools are based on a variety of verification techniques, including standard verification scores for gridded and point statistics as well as more advanced statistical measures, such as neighbourhood, object-based and intensity-scale decomposition approaches for spatial statistics. The observational data that used against the meteorological products were coming from the MADIS²⁶ system.

The meteorological products of the temperature and humidity at 2 m height, the wind speed at 10m high, the daily accumulated precipitation and the occurrence of the precipitation event were compared against observational data from surface weather stations. The occurrence of a precipitation event was treated as a categorical variable, while all the other atmospheric fields were treated as continuous variables. To match the meteorological products and observations on the horizontal plane inverse distance weighted interpolation of 9 points was used for temperature, humidity and wind speed, while nearest neighbour interpolation was applied for precipitation.

²⁴ Murphy, Allan H., and Robert L. Winkler. (1987). A general framework for forecast verification. *Monthly Weather Review*. 115.7 (1987): 1330-1338.

²⁵ <http://www.dtcenter.org/met/users/index.php>

²⁶ <https://madis.noaa.gov/>

6.3 Statistical Measures of Verification of Continuous Variables

The statistical measures that used to verify the continuous atmospheric fields of temperature and humidity at 2m high, wind speed and direction at 10m high, and the amount of daily precipitation are the following:

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** Mean absolute error is a measure of the absolute error between forecast and observation. MAE is less influenced by large errors and does not depend on the mean error. A perfect forecast would have MAE=0.
- **Mean Error (ME):** Mean error is a measure of overall bias of the forecast. An identical forecast would have ME=0.

Statistical Measures of Verification of Categorical Variables

The statistical measures that were used to verify discontinuous atmospheric fields, like precipitation are describing below:

- **Probability of Detection (POD):** Probability of detection is the fraction of the events where correctly forecasted to occur. POD ranges between 0 and 1, and the best forecast has a POD value equal to 1.
- **False Alarm Rate (FAR):** False alarm rate is the proportion of forecasts of the event occurring for which the event did not occur. FAR ranges between 0 and 1 and the best forecast have a FAR value equal to 0.
- **Equitable Threat Score (ETS):** Equitable threat score is based on CSI, corrected for the numbers of hits that would be expected by chance. ETS ranges from -1/3 to 1. The perfect forecast would have an ETS equal to 1, and a no skill forecast would have an ETS equal to 0.

Results for the Continuous Variables

Table 21 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Relative Humidity at 2m Height (All Pilots 2018).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	1.558	-0.684	3.693	8.989	7.787	10.226
24	2.792	1.350	4.409	8.867	7.998	9.839
36	9.666	7.784	11.354	12.356	10.872	13.872
48	11.470	9.656	13.355	13.861	12.489	15.274
60	1.639	-0.547	3.734	8.134	6.924	9.395
72	2.937	1.450	4.553	9.047	8.181	10.002
84	9.040	6.938	10.881	12.052	10.684	13.423
96	10.513	8.725	12.432	13.059	11.636	14.492
108	0.026	-2.478	2.299	9.352	7.854	10.789
120	2.108	0.220	3.914	9.596	8.565	10.655
132	7.886	6.024	9.823	11.673	10.205	13.199
144	10.824	8.997	12.676	13.014	11.615	14.393
156	-1.764	-4.580	0.896	10.349	8.627	12.127
168	4.430	-4.218	11.591	12.841	7.604	18.736

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Table 22 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Relative Humidity at 2m Height (All Pilots 2019).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	2.187	-0.292	3.971	9.802	8.048	10.311
24	3.024	1.555	5.050	9.020	8.603	10.347
36	10.282	8.508	11.603	12.967	11.300	14.348
48	11.840	10.570	13.536	14.448	12.771	15.405
60	2.175	-0.261	4.645	9.037	7.811	9.816
72	3.464	1.968	5.518	9.690	8.307	10.171
84	9.278	7.628	11.241	13.044	11.492	13.503
96	11.029	9.001	13.071	13.368	12.435	15.318
108	0.620	-2.199	2.397	9.810	8.051	11.058
120	2.600	1.211	3.920	9.831	9.555	11.561
132	8.106	6.611	10.181	11.719	10.640	14.100
144	11.295	9.356	13.179	13.215	11.912	15.078
156	-1.690	-4.034	1.390	10.385	9.345	12.796
168	5.027	-3.587	12.093	13.161	8.565	18.950

Table 23 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Temperature at 2m Height (All pilots 2018).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	0.086	-0.243	0.394	1.374	1.206	1.551
24	0.310	0.118	0.516	1.057	0.937	1.178
36	-1.074	-1.366	-0.779	1.670	1.486	1.885
48	-1.051	-1.294	-0.800	1.500	1.321	1.693
60	0.369	0.007	0.703	1.474	1.276	1.678
72	0.333	0.122	0.525	1.129	1.005	1.266
84	-0.812	-1.120	-0.520	1.611	1.414	1.812
96	-0.803	-1.056	-0.527	1.485	1.311	1.656
108	0.653	0.318	1.029	1.528	1.311	1.760
120	0.657	0.448	0.865	1.259	1.116	1.404
132	-0.408	-0.724	-0.078	1.617	1.413	1.845
144	-0.559	-0.840	-0.297	1.431	1.235	1.616
156	0.927	0.561	1.340	1.690	1.434	1.962
168	0.893	0.650	1.151	1.450	1.274	1.619

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Table 24 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Temperature at 2m Height (All pilots 2019).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	1.004	0.305	1.078	2.308	1.517	1.763
24	0.397	0.670	1.101	1.571	0.997	2.146
36	-0.296	-1.049	0.025	2.051	1.824	2.225
48	-0.875	-0.316	-0.250	2.261	1.537	1.799
60	1.052	0.983	0.943	1.950	1.713	1.778
72	1.076	0.489	1.282	1.774	1.061	1.787
84	0.100	-0.871	0.314	2.481	1.952	1.870
96	-0.591	-0.584	-0.327	1.869	1.975	1.761
108	1.559	0.892	1.432	2.272	2.250	2.331
120	1.123	1.204	1.163	1.812	1.555	1.439
132	-0.382	-0.587	0.104	2.040	2.129	1.922
144	0.217	-0.090	0.228	1.525	1.616	2.106
156	1.006	1.007	1.960	2.277	2.218	2.088
168	1.525	0.888	1.331	1.563	2.202	2.136

Table 25 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Wind Speed at 10m Height (All pilots 2018)

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	1.255	0.941	1.604	1.681	1.453	1.925
24	1.123	0.834	1.422	1.800	1.596	1.996
36	0.923	0.595	1.266	1.855	1.625	2.091
48	1.173	0.816	1.524	1.957	1.684	2.233
60	1.455	1.097	1.801	1.872	1.615	2.149
72	1.429	1.092	1.773	2.118	1.894	2.365
84	1.346	0.999	1.707	2.172	1.941	2.411
96	1.244	0.822	1.648	2.088	1.805	2.398
108	1.576	1.186	1.940	1.812	1.504	2.148
120	1.527	1.180	1.870	2.198	1.958	2.442
132	1.300	0.926	1.717	2.163	1.900	2.446
144	1.030	0.620	1.389	1.962	1.719	2.225
156	1.527	1.156	1.931	1.908	1.624	2.230
168	1.706	1.379	2.053	2.340	2.097	2.620

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Table 26 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Wind Speed at 10m Height (All pilots 2019)

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	1.909	0.970	1.723	2.480	1.707	2.046
24	1.805	0.987	2.417	2.096	1.874	2.586
36	1.219	1.213	1.322	1.884	2.419	2.098
48	1.908	1.463	2.283	1.967	1.869	3.107
60	2.071	1.519	1.873	1.970	2.063	2.151
72	2.261	1.737	2.688	2.164	1.909	2.845
84	1.634	1.024	1.711	2.502	2.138	3.257
96	1.469	1.441	1.889	2.639	2.002	3.076
108	2.412	1.616	2.171	1.997	2.061	2.729
120	1.661	1.881	2.591	3.141	1.965	2.882
132	1.495	1.611	1.851	2.305	2.111	3.094
144	2.008	0.646	1.876	2.159	2.230	2.544
156	1.630	1.615	2.403	2.698	2.013	2.668
168	2.344	1.409	2.607	3.215	2.976	3.618

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Table 27 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Mean Sea Level Pressure (Pa) (All pilots 2018).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	-13.871	-33.155	5.725	78.054	66.103	88.798
24	-4.608	-18.475	9.837	73.998	65.894	82.311
36	-24.428	-44.040	-4.903	97.538	85.264	110.088
48	-17.070	-33.671	1.233	89.558	78.570	100.931
60	-47.755	-68.621	-27.251	91.992	75.243	107.672
72	-27.691	-43.531	-12.404	88.220	78.250	97.968
84	-59.218	-82.263	-37.047	128.246	112.502	143.962
96	-15.734	-34.868	1.942	94.524	82.359	106.333
108	-67.598	-91.806	-42.770	106.212	89.615	124.668
120	-47.160	-62.666	-32.135	89.631	80.008	99.363
132	-80.150	-101.550	-59.200	130.566	116.889	145.161
144	-23.094	-42.211	-5.299	92.394	81.067	104.963
156	-90.272	-114.244	-68.040	113.794	96.046	132.418
168	-51.924	-71.125	-32.222	109.461	96.343	123.235

Table 28 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Mean Sea Level Pressure (Pa) (All pilots 2019).

Lead Time (hours)	ME	ME_BCL	ME_BCU	MAE	MAE_BCL	MAE_BCU
12	-12.955	-32.379	6.618	78.567	66.363	89.302
24	-4.392	-18.204	10.717	74.989	66.701	82.541
36	-23.493	-43.645	-4.277	97.613	85.690	110.836
48	-16.121	-33.090	2.204	89.871	79.064	101.458
60	-46.899	-68.570	-26.977	92.142	75.969	108.234
72	-27.341	-43.382	-11.933	88.951	78.825	98.890
84	-58.522	-82.155	-36.606	129.123	113.164	144.707
96	-15.384	-34.714	2.691	95.318	83.353	106.346
108	-67.323	-91.114	-42.743	106.713	89.626	124.841
120	-46.275	-61.928	-31.319	90.274	80.459	99.661
132	-79.540	-100.857	-58.982	131.297	117.239	145.830
144	-22.335	-42.000	-4.563	92.604	81.668	105.650
156	-90.119	-113.581	-67.988	114.436	96.775	132.501
168	-51.795	-70.334	-31.750	109.783	96.852	123.829

Results of the Categorical Variables

Table 29 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Precipitation (All pilots 2019).

Lead Time (hours)	PODY	FAR	ETS
24	0.737	0.650	0.234
48	0.909	0.608	0.273
72	0.889	0.686	0.222
96	0.818	0.633	0.234
120	0.889	0.600	0.311
144	0.810	0.685	0.185
168	0.722	0.667	0.222

Table 30 - Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean error for: Precipitation (All pilots 2019).

Lead Time (hours)	PODY	FAR	ETS
24	0.836	0.678	0.289
48	0.92	0.622	0.324
72	0.819	0.684	0.267
96	0.824	0.656	0.263
120	0.876	0.612	0.296
144	0.754	0.674	0.237
168	0.702	0.652	0.214

7 Conclusions

The project DIANA address the detection and the monitoring of non-authorized irrigation and abstractions in water-scarce environments by using leading-edge EO technologies.

In this framework, different methodologies to obtain the maps of irrigated areas, the maps of irrigation water consumption and abstracted volumes were defined, applied and tested for each project's pilot zones. The validation of these products and services provides encouraging results and highlights the key role of Earth Observation data for the assessment and management of the water resources in agriculture.

To this end, the definition of validated methodologies, such as those developed in DIANA, is an essential requirement to establish robust and fast processing chains.

The experiences carried out within the DIANA project have confirmed that Earth Observation combined with meteorological, modelled and in-situ data is a mature technology ready to be transferred to operational applications and to be used as a useful tool for the water managers in day-to-day operations.

Particularly, the comparison and validation process has demonstrated the capability of the time series of the optical data (for Italian, Spanish and Romanian pilot area) and radar data (for Romanian pilot area) to estimate the maps of irrigated areas with high thematic accuracy.

The validation process has been performed for each pilot areas also for the irrigation season 2019, including a robust analysis of the OPTRAM, and Tu Wien algorithms, proposed for the Diana Benchmark exercise with the aim to improve the detection of irrigated areas process, taking into account the soil moisture data estimated from different EO platforms.

As a conclusion, we can affirm that the OPTRAM model has demonstrated to be capable to distinguish the irrigated crop from not irrigated crop and the approach can be transferred to different geographical regions, with different crop types, climate and management.

It confirms that additional information derived in the SWIR spectrum is a valuable data source for improving irrigated area mapping in a variety of environmental conditions. The outcomes of WP2 of DIANA project represent an excellent starting point for further research activities which exploit the information provided by sentinel satellites.

